

Formal Verification of the Ward–Takahashi Identities in QED and QCD in Lean 4

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12 January 2025

Abstract

We present a formal algebraic verification of the Ward–Takahashi identity in quantum electrodynamics (QED) and its analogue in quantum chromodynamics (QCD) using the Lean 4 proof assistant with the Mathlib mathematical library. The verification is carried out at tree level within a general algebraic framework: the Dirac algebra is modelled as an abstract F -algebra A , and gamma matrices as elements of A . The inverse fermion propagator is defined as $S^{-1}(p) = \not{p} - m$. We prove that the contraction of the momentum transfer with the tree-level vertex equals the difference of inverse propagators. For QCD, we extend the result to include colour generators, using the commutativity of the algebra map (which encodes the physical fact that colour and Dirac structures act on independent spaces). All proofs are checked by the Lean 4 kernel and depend only on Mathlib and the standard axioms (`propext`, `Classical.choice`, `Quot.sound`).

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1 Introduction

The Ward–Takahashi identity [1, 2] is a fundamental consequence of the $U(1)$ gauge invariance of quantum electrodynamics. It relates the longitudinal part of the electron–photon vertex function $\Gamma^\mu(p', p)$ to the difference of inverse fermion propagators:

$$q_\mu \Gamma^\mu(p', p) = S^{-1}(p') - S^{-1}(p), \quad q = p' - p. \quad (1)$$

This identity constrains the ultraviolet divergences of the vertex correction and ensures the renormalisability of QED. In quantum chromodynamics (QCD), the non-abelian gauge symmetry $SU(3)_c$ leads to a generalisation involving colour generators T^a , known at higher orders as the Slavnov–Taylor identities [3, 4].

At tree level, the vertex function reduces to $\Gamma^\mu = \gamma^\mu$ (in QED) or $\Gamma_{ij}^\mu = T_{ij}^a \gamma^\mu$ (in QCD), and the identities become purely algebraic statements about the Dirac and colour algebras. This makes them amenable to formal verification.

In this work, we formalise these identities in Lean 4 [5] using the Mathlib library [6]. The Dirac algebra is represented as an abstract F -algebra A over a field F , with gamma matrices $\gamma^\mu \in A$, $\mu = 0, 1, 2, 3$. The key advantage of this approach is its generality: the proofs do not rely on a specific matrix representation of the gamma matrices, but only on the algebraic structure.

2 Definitions

We work over a field F and an F -algebra A . The gamma matrices are represented as a map $\gamma : \text{Fin } 4 \rightarrow A$, assigning to each Lorentz index $\mu \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ an element γ^μ of the algebra.

Definition 2.1 (Feynman slash). The *Feynman slash* of a 4-momentum $p = (p_0, p_1, p_2, p_3)$ is the element of the Dirac algebra defined by

$$\not{p} = \gamma^\mu p_\mu = \sum_{\mu=0}^3 \gamma^\mu p_\mu. \quad (2)$$

In Lean 4, this is formalised as:

```
def slash (γ : Fin 4 → A) (p : Fin 4 → F) : A :=
  ∑ μ : Fin 4, p μ • γ μ
```

Remark 2.1. The Lean definition uses the scalar multiplication $p_\mu \bullet \gamma^\mu$ (an element of F acting on A), which corresponds to $p_\mu \cdot \gamma^\mu$ in the standard physics notation. The summation is over $\text{Fin } 4 = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$.

Definition 2.2 (Inverse fermion propagator). The *inverse fermion propagator* for a fermion of mass m and 4-momentum p is

$$S^{-1}(p) = \not{p} - m. \quad (3)$$

In Lean 4:

```
def S_inv (γ : Fin 4 → A) (m : A) (p : Fin 4 → F) : A :=
  slash γ p - m
```

Definition 2.3 (Vertex contraction). The *contraction* of a 4-momentum q with a vertex function Γ^μ is

$$q_\mu \Gamma^\mu = \sum_{\mu=0}^3 q_\mu \Gamma^\mu. \quad (4)$$

In Lean 4:

```
def contract (q : Fin 4 → F) (Γ : Fin 4 → A) : A :=
  ∑ μ : Fin 4, q μ • Γ μ
```

Remark 2.2. The Feynman slash is a special case of the vertex contraction: $\not{p} = p_\mu \gamma^\mu = \text{contract}(p, \gamma)$. In Lean this is witnessed by the definitional equality `slash_eq_contract`.

3 Helper Lemma

The following lemma expresses the linearity of the Feynman slash with respect to subtraction of momenta.

Lemma 3.1 (Linearity of the slash). For any momenta p and p' ,

$$(\not{p}' \not{-} p) = \not{p}' - \not{p}, \quad (5)$$

where $(\not{p}' \not{-} p)$ denotes $\sum_\mu (p'_\mu - p_\mu) \gamma^\mu$.

In Lean 4:

```
theorem slash_sub (γ : Fin 4 → A) (p p' : Fin 4 → F) :
  slash γ (fun μ => p' μ - p μ) = slash γ p' - slash γ p
```

Proof. By unfolding the definition of the slash and using the distributivity of scalar multiplication over subtraction (`sub_smul`), together with the linearity of finite sums (`sum_sub_distrib`). \square

4 QED Ward–Takahashi Identity

4.1 Asymmetric form

Theorem 4.1 (Ward–Takahashi identity, asymmetric form). For any momenta p, p' and mass m , with $q = p' - p$:

$$q_\mu \gamma^\mu = S^{-1}(p') - S^{-1}(p). \quad (6)$$

In Lean 4:

```
theorem QED_Ward_Takahashi_asymmetric
  (γ : Fin 4 → A) (m : A)
  (p p' : Fin 4 → F) :
  contract (fun μ => p' μ - p μ) γ =
    S_inv γ m p' - S_inv γ m p
```

Proof. Unfold the definitions of `S_inv`, `contract`, and `slash`. The identity then reduces to

$$\sum_\mu (p'_\mu - p_\mu) \gamma^\mu = \left(\sum_\mu p'_\mu \gamma^\mu - m \right) - \left(\sum_\mu p_\mu \gamma^\mu - m \right).$$

The mass terms cancel, and the right-hand side equals $\sum_\mu p'_\mu \gamma^\mu - \sum_\mu p_\mu \gamma^\mu$, which equals the left-hand side by the distributivity of scalar multiplication over subtraction. \square

4.2 Symmetric form

Theorem 4.2 (Ward–Takahashi identity, symmetric form). For any momentum p , transfer momentum q , and mass m , assuming $\text{char}(F) \neq 2$:

$$q_\mu \gamma^\mu = S^{-1}\left(p + \frac{q}{2}\right) - S^{-1}\left(p - \frac{q}{2}\right). \quad (7)$$

In Lean 4:

```
theorem QED_Ward_Takahashi_symmetric
  [NeZero (2 : F)]
  (γ : Fin 4 → A) (m : A)
  (p q : Fin 4 → F) :
  contract q γ =
    S_inv γ m (fun μ => p μ + q μ / 2) -
    S_inv γ m (fun μ => p μ - q μ / 2)
```

Proof. Set $p_+ = p + q/2$ and $p_- = p - q/2$. Then $p_+ - p_- = q$. The result follows from the asymmetric form (Theorem 4.1) applied with p_- in place of p and p_+ in place of p' . \square

4.3 Full identity with transverse corrections

Theorem 4.3 (Full Ward–Takahashi identity). Let $\delta\Gamma^\mu$ be a one-loop vertex correction satisfying the transversality condition

$$q_\mu \delta\Gamma^\mu = 0, \quad q = p' - p. \quad (8)$$

Then the full vertex $\Gamma^\mu = \gamma^\mu + \delta\Gamma^\mu$ satisfies the Ward–Takahashi identity:

$$q_\mu \Gamma^\mu = S^{-1}(p') - S^{-1}(p). \quad (9)$$

In Lean 4:

```
theorem QED_Ward_Takahashi_full
  (γ δΓ : Fin 4 → A) (m : A)
  (p p' : Fin 4 → F)
  (h_transverse :
    contract (fun μ => p' μ - p μ) δΓ = 0) :
  contract (fun μ => p' μ - p μ)
    (fun μ => γ μ + δΓ μ) =
    S_inv γ m p' - S_inv γ m p
```

Proof. By linearity of the contraction, $q_\mu(\gamma^\mu + \delta\Gamma^\mu) = q_\mu\gamma^\mu + q_\mu\delta\Gamma^\mu$. The second term vanishes by the transversality hypothesis, and the first equals $S^{-1}(p') - S^{-1}(p)$ by Theorem 4.1. \square

5 QCD Ward–Takahashi Identity

In QCD, the quark–gluon vertex at tree level carries both Dirac and colour indices. For a colour generator $T^a \in \text{Mat}_N(F)$ (where N is the number of colours), the tree-level vertex is

$$\Gamma_{ij}^\mu = T_{ij}^a \gamma^\mu. \quad (10)$$

The inverse quark propagator is diagonal in colour space:

$$[S^{-1}(p)]_{ij} = \delta_{ij}(\not{p} - m). \quad (11)$$

5.1 Commutativity of colour and Dirac structures

A key algebraic ingredient is that scalars from F (such as the colour matrix entries T_{ij}) commute with all elements of the algebra A . In the physical setting, this reflects the fact that colour and Dirac structures act on independent spaces.

```
theorem algebraMap_comm (c : F) (a : A) :
  algebraMap F A c * a = a * algebraMap F A c
```

5.2 Entry-wise form

Theorem 5.1 (QCD Ward–Takahashi identity, entry-wise). For a colour generator $T \in \text{Mat}_N(F)$, momenta p, p' , and mass m :

$$q_\mu \Gamma_{ij}^\mu = \sum_\mu (p'_\mu - p_\mu) T_{ij} \gamma^\mu = S^{-1}(p') \cdot T_{ij} - T_{ij} \cdot S^{-1}(p), \quad (12)$$

where the products are taken in the Dirac algebra A via the algebra map, i.e. $T_{ij} \equiv \text{algebraMap}_F^A(T_{ij})$.

In Lean 4:

```
theorem QCD_Ward_Takahashi_tree {N : ℕ}
  (γ : Fin 4 → A) (m : A)
  (p p' : Fin 4 → F)
  (T : Matrix (Fin N) (Fin N) F)
  (i j : Fin N) :
  (∑ μ : Fin 4,
    (p' μ - p μ) • (T i j • γ μ)) =
  S_inv γ m p' * algebraMap F A (T i j) -
  algebraMap F A (T i j) * S_inv γ m p
```

Proof. Factor out T_{ij} from the left-hand side using the associativity of scalar multiplication and the definition of the algebra map. The result then follows from the QED identity (Theorem 4.1) and the commutativity of colour scalars with Dirac algebra elements. \square

5.3 Matrix form

Theorem 5.2 (QCD Ward–Takahashi identity, matrix form). Let $S_{\text{color}}(p) = S^{-1}(p) \cdot \mathbf{1}_N$ be the inverse propagator in colour space, and let $T_A = T.\text{map}(\text{algebraMap } F \ A)$. Then:

$$\sum_\mu q_\mu \Gamma^\mu = S_{\text{color}}(p') \cdot T_A - T_A \cdot S_{\text{color}}(p). \quad (13)$$

In Lean 4:

```
theorem QCD_Ward_Takahashi_matrix {N : ℕ}
  [DecidableEq (Fin N)]
  (γ : Fin 4 → A) (m : A)
  (p p' : Fin 4 → F)
  (T : Matrix (Fin N) (Fin N) F) :
  (Matrix.of fun i j =>
    ∑ μ : Fin 4,
      (p' μ - p μ) • (T i j • γ μ)) =
  (Matrix.diagonal
    fun _ => S_inv γ m p') *
  (T.map (algebraMap F A)) -
  (T.map (algebraMap F A)) *
  (Matrix.diagonal fun _ => S_inv γ m p)
```

Proof. Follows by verifying the identity entry-wise using Theorem 5.1 and the definitions of matrix multiplication and diagonal matrices. \square

6 Special Cases and Numerical Verification

6.1 Identity at $p = 0$

Setting $p = 0$ in the asymmetric identity yields a useful consistency check:

$$q_\mu \gamma^\mu = S^{-1}(q) - S^{-1}(0). \quad (14)$$

Both sides equal q , since $S^{-1}(q) - S^{-1}(0) = (q - m) - (0 - m) = q$.

```

theorem QED_Ward_Takahashi_at_zero
  (γ : Fin 4 → A) (m : A)
  (q : Fin 4 → F) :
  contract q γ =
    S_inv γ m q -
    S_inv γ m (fun _ => (0 : F))

```

6.2 Numerical check over \mathbb{Q}

As a concrete sanity check, we verify the QED identity numerically over the rationals with $p = (1, 0, 0, 0)$, $p' = (1, 1, 0, 0)$, $\gamma^\mu = 1$ for all μ (the commutative case), and $m = 1$.

```

theorem QED_numerical_check :
  let p : Fin 4 → ℚ := ![1, 0, 0, 0]
  let p' : Fin 4 → ℚ := ![1, 1, 0, 0]
  let γ : Fin 4 → ℚ := ![1, 1, 1, 1]
  let m : ℚ := 1
  (contract (F := ℚ) (A := ℚ)
    (fun μ => p' μ - p μ) γ : ℚ) =
    S_inv (F := ℚ) (A := ℚ) γ m p' -
    S_inv (F := ℚ) (A := ℚ) γ m p

```

This follows directly from Theorem 4.1 by instantiation.

7 Discussion

The formalisation presented here demonstrates that the tree-level Ward–Takahashi identities of QED and QCD can be verified purely algebraically, without reference to a specific representation of the gamma matrices. The proofs rely only on:

- the ring structure of the algebra A ;
- the distributivity of scalar multiplication over addition and subtraction;
- the commutativity of the algebra map $F \rightarrow A$ (for the QCD case).

The Lean 4 formalisation provides a machine-checked guarantee of correctness. All proofs compile under the standard axioms (`propext`, `Classical.choice`, `Quot.sound`) with no use of `sorry`.

A natural direction for further work is the formalisation of the full (all-orders) Ward–Takahashi identity, which requires a treatment of loop integrals and regularisation. The Slavnov–Taylor identities for non-abelian gauge theories at higher loop orders present additional challenges due to the role of ghost fields and BRST symmetry.

8 Conclusion

We have formally verified the tree-level Ward–Takahashi identity in both QED and QCD using Lean 4 and Mathlib. The QED identity is proved in asymmetric, symmetric, and full (with transverse corrections) forms. The QCD generalisation is established both entry-wise and in matrix form. The formalisation is self-contained and depends only on the standard Mathlib algebraic hierarchy.

Acknowledgements. The author thanks the Mathlib community for maintaining the comprehensive mathematical library that makes this formalisation possible.

References

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- [4] J.C. Taylor, “Ward identities and charge renormalization of the Yang–Mills field,” *Nucl. Phys. B* **33**, 436–444 (1971).
- [5] L. de Moura *et al.*, “The Lean 4 theorem prover and programming language,” <https://lean-lang.org/> (2021).
- [6] The Mathlib Community, “Mathlib: the Lean mathematical library,” <https://github.com/leanprover-community/mathlib4>.

A Full Lean Source Code

The complete Lean 4 source file `WardTakahashi.lean` is reproduced below.

```
import Mathlib

open Finset BigOperators Matrix

namespace WardTakahashi

variable {F : Type*} [Field F]
variable {A : Type*} [Ring A] [Algebra F A]

-- Definitions

def slash (γ : Fin 4 → A) (p : Fin 4 → F) : A :=
  ∑ μ : Fin 4, p μ • γ μ

def S_inv (γ : Fin 4 → A) (m : A) (p : Fin 4 → F) : A :=
  slash γ p - m

def contract (q : Fin 4 → F) (Γ : Fin 4 → A) : A :=
  ∑ μ : Fin 4, q μ • Γ μ

theorem slash_eq_contract (γ : Fin 4 → A) (q : Fin 4 → F) :
  slash γ q = contract q γ := rfl

-- Helper lemmas
```

```

theorem slash_sub ( $\gamma : \text{Fin } 4 \rightarrow A$ ) ( $p \ p' : \text{Fin } 4 \rightarrow F$ ) :
  slash  $\gamma$  (fun  $\mu \Rightarrow p' \ \mu - p \ \mu$ ) = slash  $\gamma$   $p'$  - slash  $\gamma$   $p$  := by
  unfold slash;
  simp +decide only [sub_smul, sum_sub_distrib]

-- QED Ward-Takahashi Identity

theorem QED_Ward_Takahashi_asymmetric
  ( $\gamma : \text{Fin } 4 \rightarrow A$ ) ( $m : A$ ) ( $p \ p' : \text{Fin } 4 \rightarrow F$ ) :
  contract (fun  $\mu \Rightarrow p' \ \mu - p \ \mu$ )  $\gamma$  =
    S_inv  $\gamma$   $m$   $p'$  - S_inv  $\gamma$   $m$   $p$  := by
  unfold S_inv contract slash
  simp +decide [sub_smul, Finset.sum_sub_distrib]

theorem QED_Ward_Takahashi_symmetric [NeZero (2 : F)]
  ( $\gamma : \text{Fin } 4 \rightarrow A$ ) ( $m : A$ ) ( $p \ q : \text{Fin } 4 \rightarrow F$ ) :
  contract  $q$   $\gamma$  =
    S_inv  $\gamma$   $m$  (fun  $\mu \Rightarrow p \ \mu + q \ \mu / 2$ ) -
    S_inv  $\gamma$   $m$  (fun  $\mu \Rightarrow p \ \mu - q \ \mu / 2$ ) := by
  convert QED_Ward_Takahashi_asymmetric  $\gamma$   $m$ 
    (fun  $\mu \Rightarrow p \ \mu - q \ \mu / 2$ ) (fun  $\mu \Rightarrow p \ \mu + q \ \mu / 2$ )
  using 1;
  simp +decide [ $\leftarrow$  two_mul, mul_left_comm, div_eq_mul_inv];
  rw [mul_inv_cancel_0 (NeZero.ne _)]; norm_num

theorem QED_Ward_Takahashi_full
  ( $\gamma \ \delta\Gamma : \text{Fin } 4 \rightarrow A$ ) ( $m : A$ ) ( $p \ p' : \text{Fin } 4 \rightarrow F$ )
  (h_transverse :
    contract (fun  $\mu \Rightarrow p' \ \mu - p \ \mu$ )  $\delta\Gamma$  = 0) :
  contract (fun  $\mu \Rightarrow p' \ \mu - p \ \mu$ ) (fun  $\mu \Rightarrow \gamma \ \mu + \delta\Gamma \ \mu$ ) =
    S_inv  $\gamma$   $m$   $p'$  - S_inv  $\gamma$   $m$   $p$  := by
  have h_contract_linear :
    contract (fun  $\mu \Rightarrow p' \ \mu - p \ \mu$ ) (fun  $\mu \Rightarrow \gamma \ \mu + \delta\Gamma \ \mu$ ) =
      contract (fun  $\mu \Rightarrow p' \ \mu - p \ \mu$ )  $\gamma$  +
      contract (fun  $\mu \Rightarrow p' \ \mu - p \ \mu$ )  $\delta\Gamma$  := by
    unfold contract;
    simp +decide [Finset.sum_add_distrib];
  rw [h_contract_linear, h_transverse, add_zero,
    QED_Ward_Takahashi_asymmetric]

-- QCD Ward-Takahashi Identity

theorem algebraMap_comm ( $c : F$ ) ( $a : A$ ) :
  algebraMap F A  $c$  *  $a$  =  $a$  * algebraMap F A  $c$  := by
  convert (Algebra.commutates _ _) using 1

theorem QCD_Ward_Takahashi_tree {N : ℕ}
  ( $\gamma : \text{Fin } 4 \rightarrow A$ ) ( $m : A$ )
  ( $p \ p' : \text{Fin } 4 \rightarrow F$ )
  (T : Matrix (Fin N) (Fin N) F)
  (i j : Fin N) :
  ( $\sum \mu : \text{Fin } 4,$ 
    ( $p' \ \mu - p \ \mu$ ) • (T i j •  $\gamma \ \mu$ )) =
    S_inv  $\gamma$   $m$   $p'$  * algebraMap F A (T i j) -
    algebraMap F A (T i j) * S_inv  $\gamma$   $m$   $p$  := by
  convert congr_arg (fun x : A => algebraMap F A (T i j) * x)
    (QED_Ward_Takahashi_asymmetric  $\gamma$   $m$   $p \ p'$ ) using 1;

```

```

· simp +decide [contract, Finset.mul_sum _ _ _, smul_smul];
  simp +decide [Algebra.smul_def, mul_assoc];
· simp +decide [mul_sub, Algebra.commutates]

theorem QCD_Ward_Takahashi_matrix {N : ℕ}
  [DecidableEq (Fin N)]
  (γ : Fin 4 → A) (m : A)
  (p p' : Fin 4 → F)
  (T : Matrix (Fin N) (Fin N) F) :
  (Matrix.of fun i j =>
    ∑ μ : Fin 4,
    (p' μ - p μ) • (T i j • γ μ)) =
  (Matrix.diagonal fun _ => S_inv γ m p') *
  (T.map (algebraMap F A)) -
  (T.map (algebraMap F A)) *
  (Matrix.diagonal fun _ => S_inv γ m p) := by
  ext i j;
  simp +decide [Matrix.mul_apply,
    Matrix.diagonal_apply];
  convert QCD_Ward_Takahashi_tree γ m p p' T i j
  using 1

-- Special Case: p = 0

theorem QED_Ward_Takahashi_at_zero
  (γ : Fin 4 → A) (m : A)
  (q : Fin 4 → F) :
  contract q γ =
  S_inv γ m q -
  S_inv γ m (fun _ => (0 : F)) := by
  have := QED_Ward_Takahashi_asymmetric
  γ m (fun _ => 0) q
  simp at this
  exact this

-- Numerical verification over ℚ

theorem QED_numerical_check :
  let p : Fin 4 → ℚ := ![1, 0, 0, 0]
  let p' : Fin 4 → ℚ := ![1, 1, 0, 0]
  let γ : Fin 4 → ℚ := ![1, 1, 1, 1]
  let m : ℚ := 1
  (contract (F := ℚ) (A := ℚ)
    (fun μ => p' μ - p μ) γ : ℚ) =
  S_inv (F := ℚ) (A := ℚ) γ m p' -
  S_inv (F := ℚ) (A := ℚ) γ m p := by
  convert QED_Ward_Takahashi_asymmetric _ _ _ _
  using 1

end WardTakahashi

```